

Research Data Management Workflows and maDMPs

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What was the task defined for the hackathon?

Since the main funding agencies are now requiring DMPs to be included in grant applications, institutions need to implement a workflow for creating the DMP or improving existing ones. Researchers in different institutions use different methodologies for DMP creation. Some plans are created with institutional support, others are created by researchers without any support. However, almost all institutions have started to develop their Research Data Management (RDM) workflow to help their researchers during the DMP creation by using their own methodology. Moreover, according to DCS-WG, the maDMP principle will help in exchanging DMP between platforms and systems.

During the Hackathon, the work of our group focused on the analysis of existing RDM Workflows from different institutions, namely Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science (INESC TEC), Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences of the University of Porto (FPCEUP), Portuguese Institute of Oncology of Porto (IPO-Porto) and George Washington University (GWU). Moreover, we also analysed the DMP creation process on these institutions, and compared our methodologies against the maDMP concept to identify elements that require changes (addition, elimination, edition) in our DMPs to make them machine-actionable. We also identified some requirements to improve our institutions RDM Workflows and turn our DMP compliant with the maDMP concept.

Why is this task important?

The final report of this work aims to serve as guidance for the implementation of maDMP principles in institutions' workflows and for the improvement of RDM workflows in general. This work shows the starting point for the application of maDMP standard in the institutions, where well-defined and established RDM workflows do not yet exist. It is a use case with real

institutions corresponding to different types of organisation, where researchers require support for both the creation of DMP and all RDM activities in general. This work shows which processes and structures must be analysed at the beginning to understand the current situation in the institution in relation to the DMP. Moreover, it shows how elements of maDMP standard can be mapped to elements used in the creation of DMP on institutions, and how these elements can be improved and tested.

What did you achieve (and how) during the hackathon?

During the Hackathon, our team analysed the schemes, structures, workflows, use cases and other relevant documentation related to the maDMP proposed by the DCS-WG. Then, we analysed the existing RDM Workflows, DMP support systems, DMP creation processes, and DMP content structure with regards to the elements used during the DMP creation on different institutions, namely [INESC TEC](#), [FPCEUP](#), [IPO-Porto](#) and [GWU](#). All analysis are represented as figures, mainly depicting schemes, for better and easier understanding with the short description (see [InsTmaDMP report](#)). This first part of our work helped us understand the current situation in our institutions related to RDM and DMP, and gave us an overview of the existing lacks, and how we can improve our existing RDM Workflow and DMP processes.

The second part of our work focused on the comparison of all the existing schemes and on the creation of the list of items for improvement, of the differences we found, and the identification of the elements that need to be changed in order to be consistent with the maDMP standard. Due to the quantity of information that we need to analyse and compare we will continue this task after the Hackathon for more detail. At the moment we have created several improved schemes as our proposal of improvement of RDM Workflow, DMP support system and DMP content structure (see Figure 1, 2, 3, 4), that demonstrate our vision of the improvement in our institutions according to maDMP principle. In general, we identified the following points:

- All RDM Workflows from our analysed institutions need to add many additional mechanisms and processes.
- All DMP support systems of our analysed institutions need to implement more types of actors and more internal processes to conform to the proposed maDMP system.
- In all analysed institutions only the planning phase is precisely defined using tools such as DMPOnline, DMPTool. However, the results of this work showed that this phase also needs improvement according to maDMP.
- The DMP/maDMP should be associated with the responsible researcher(s).
- The DMP/maDMP should be associated with a DataSet of the project, inserted on the RDM Workflow;
- The DMP content structures on analysed institutions are very different from maDMP principles and need to be mapped and adapted according to maDMP standards. Figure

4 shows the first attempt of adoption and application of maDMP scheme at INESC TEC. This new improved DMP content structure was validated through experiences with two researchers, who recreated existing DMP (on [farming systems](#) and [gamma radiation monitoring](#)) using the new structure. The results and feedback from researchers showed that the recreation process was quite difficult, some fields were not well understood, and seemed that this type of DMP is not very informative for domains such as biodiversity. However, the new structure has new elements that actually make sense due to their relevance since the beginning of the project. Thus, we need to improve the elements description and gather information from more experiences on different scientific domains to understand what kind of elements should be added to this scheme to attend to the needs of the different scientific domains.

Figure 1. Shema of RDM Workflow improved at FPCEUP

Figure 2. Schema of improved DMP support system at INESC TEC

Figure 3. Schema of improved DMP support system at FPCEUP

Figure 4. Improved DMP content structure at INESC TEC according maDMP

The third part of the Hackathon included the final discussion about our work in general. Even though we have several tasks incomplete and without detailed description, we perform all our planned and defined tasks for this Hackathon.

How will your work continue after the Hackathon?

After the Hackathon, we will continue to analyse all the collected information to improve our report and publish a final version. This final version of the report will contain a detailed description of all our RDM Workflows, schemes, DMP processes, the lists of the identified

elements for improvement to be implemented in the future. Moreover, we will provide a detailed description of our experiences. We will also improve our new mapped DMP structure and add a description to each field. Finally, we will complete our report with schemes, figures and descriptions of each institution, and propose possible measures to improve our RDM Workflows and DMP support systems.